

ASSESSING AWARENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN ANESTHESIA AMONG ANESTHESIA PROFESSIONALS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Anesthetic practices contribute significantly to healthcare's environmental footprint through volatile anesthetic gas emissions and medical waste. Despite global emphasis on sustainability, limited evidence exists on the awareness of such practices among anesthesia professionals in low- and middle-income countries, including Pakistan.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in four tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan. Using convenience sampling, 150 anesthesia professionals (consultants, trainees, technologists) were recruited. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire adapted from validated tools. Descriptive statistics and cross-tabulations assessed awareness, training, and institutional practices.

Results: Of the participants, 64.7% reported awareness of anesthesia's environmental impact, while 35.3% were unaware. Only 57.3% correctly identified sustainable practices such as peripheral nerve blocks and total intravenous anesthesia. Half (50.7%) had received formal training, though 88% expressed interest in further education. Additionally, 76% supported integrating sustainability education into clinical assessments, but only 36.7% reported the presence of institutional guidelines. Importantly, 78% agreed that anesthesia professionals share responsibility in addressing environmental sustainability.

Conclusion: The findings indicate a moderate level of awareness among anesthesia professionals in Peshawar, with gaps in validated knowledge and institutional support. However, strong interest in training and policy integration reflects readiness for improvement. Structured educational initiatives, institutional reforms, and policy development are crucial to advancing sustainable anesthesia practices in Pakistan, aligning local efforts with global health and climate goals.

Introduction

Environmental sustainability is a critical concept focused on preserving natural resources to ensure that future generations can meet their needs without compromising the environment (1). It emphasizes a balance between human activities and ecological health, advocating for practices that reduce pollution, conserve resources, and promote renewable methods of consumption.

Environmental sustainability (ES) refers to the responsible management of natural resources to prevent depletion and ensure ecological balance, addressing issues like resource scarcity, pollution, and climate change (1,2).

Environmental sustainability is becoming increasingly important in healthcare, particularly in anesthesia, where

practices can significantly impact the environment through waste generation and greenhouse gas emissions (3)(4).

The healthcare sector is responsible for 4.4-5.2% of total global greenhouse gas emissions, with anesthetic gases playing a significant role in this contribution (1)(5). Waste anesthetic gases (WAGs) released during surgical procedures contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, although they represent a relatively small portion of total emissions (6). fluorocarbons are the inhalational agents that contribute to manmade climate change (7). Inhaled anesthetics are greenhouse gases that contribute to climate change, accounting for approximately 3% of the healthcare sector's climate footprint in high-income nations (8). Inhalational agents like isoflurane, desflurane have 2 to 3 times higher global warming potential than CO₂ on the other hand nitrous oxide also contributes to ozone depletion (9). An estimated 200 million anesthetic procedures are performed annually, leading to emissions equivalent to 4.4 million tons of carbon dioxide, comparable to the emissions from about 1 million passenger cars (10). Overall, the cumulative effects of anesthetic gases, waste generation, and energy use highlight the need for sustainable practices in anesthesia to mitigate environmental harm. The use of halogenated anesthetic agents, such as desflurane, has been shown to account for a substantial portion of greenhouse gas emissions in operating rooms, sometimes exceeding 50% of total emissions of OR (11).

Mitigating the environmental impact of anesthetic gases can be achieved through practices similar to optimization of delivering efficiency such as total intravenous anesthesia and peripheral nerve blockades, reduction of waste, and substituting minimal harmful anesthetic agents (12)(13). The implementation of sustainable initiatives in anesthesia not only benefits the environment but can also enhance the overall quality of care, as patient safety remains a top priority (3).

Assessing awareness helps identify significant gaps in education and training related to environmental sustainability among anesthesia professionals, which is crucial for developing targeted educational programs. Many professionals report a lack of environmental training in their curriculum, highlighting the need for improvement. Understanding the current level of awareness can motivate anesthesia providers to adopt sustainable practices, as increased knowledge can lead to quantifiable reductions in waste and energy consumption in the operating room (3).

Awareness assessments can help anesthesia professionals understand how to balance patient safety with environmentally friendly practices, ensuring that

sustainable choices do not compromise care quality (14). By evaluating awareness levels, anesthesia professionals can advocate for institutional changes that support sustainability initiatives, potentially leading to the implementation of greener policies within healthcare settings(15). Assessing awareness can enhance community engagement among anesthesia professionals, encouraging them to participate in sustainability initiatives and collaborate on solutions to reduce the environmental impact of their practices (1).

Assessing awareness levels among anesthesia professionals is crucial for identifying these knowledge gaps and developing targeted educational interventions that can promote sustainable practices (14). Ultimately, fostering a culture of sustainability within anesthesia can lead to significant improvements in the environmental footprint of healthcare, aligning with global sustainability goals (2,16). Education and training on sustainable practices can empower anesthesia professionals to adopt greener techniques, such as optimizing drug dosages and improving gas delivery systems, which can lead to more efficient use of resources and reduced emissions (17).

Importance of Awareness

- Anesthesia professionals can actively implement measures to reduce their carbon footprint, contributing to broader sustainability goals within healthcare. Increased awareness can lead to quantifiable decreases in the misuse of medications and energy consumption (3).
- There is a significant lack of environmental training in anesthesia, with many professionals unaware of the environmental impact of their practices. Addressing this gap through education can empower anesthesiologists to make informed decisions that align with sustainability principles (2,14).
- Awareness can inspire anesthesia providers to advocate for sustainable practices within their institutions, potentially leading to the adoption of greener policies and practices that benefit the environment (1).
- Understanding the balance between patient safety and environmental sustainability is crucial. Anesthesia professionals must be educated on how to make environmentally friendly choices without compromising patient care (3).
- Increased awareness fosters a sense of accountability among anesthesia professionals, encouraging them to engage in community efforts aimed at promoting sustainability in healthcare (1,18).

In recent years, several studies have examined the environmental impacts of anesthesia(19). However, few

studies have assessed the level of awareness among anesthesia professionals in the subcontinent, particularly in Peshawar, Pakistan. Furthermore, addressing climate change requires targeted departmental attention, especially within the anesthesia sector of the healthcare system.

This study is important because the healthcare sector, particularly anesthesia, plays a significant role in environmental pollution due to the use of agents like sevoflurane, desflurane, and nitrous oxide that have high global warming effects. While previous studies have

Aims and Objectives

1. To assess the awareness of about environmental sustainability in anesthesia among anesthesia professionals.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional study design, which allowed us for the evaluation of awareness levels at a single point in time across a defined population. This design was appropriate for exploring relationships between awareness, and environmentally sustainable practices, and it facilitated the collection of data that is both comprehensive and time-efficient.

Data Collection Tools

A structured questionnaire was the primary data collection tool. Which is adopted from an article (20). Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Frequency distribution was used to summarize participants data and general trends in awareness.

Results and Analysis

Total of 150 participants participated in this study from both public and private hospitals across Peshawar which include Hayatabad Medical Complex Peshawar, Institute of Kidney Diseases Peshawar, Leady Reading Hospital Peshawar, and MMC General Hospital Peshawar. Ethical approval from each hospital was taken for the data collection procedure and questionnaires was distributed among anesthesia professionals to record their responses for our research. In order to maintain confidentiality, we do not ask their names and also provided the consent form both in English and in Urdu. After reading the consent they recorded their responses with us with the help of questionnaire (20).

looked at the environmental impacts of anesthesia, few have examined how well anesthesia professionals understand these issues, especially in Peshawar, Pakistan. By focusing on both general anesthesia and the eco-friendly option of peripheral nerve blocks (PNBs), this research aims to assess current awareness. These results will help guide training programs, shape hospital policies, and encourage the adoption of greener anesthesia practices, ultimately reducing the environmental impact of healthcare.

Study setting

This study was conducted in City University of Science and Information Technology Peshawar.

Population of the Study

The targeted population comprised anesthesia professionals, including anesthetists, trainee medical, medical officers, officer of anesthesia and anesthesia technologist. This population was chosen as they were directly responsible for implementing practices and were well-positioned to influence the adoption of environmentally sustainable methods.

Demographic data

A total of 150 anesthesia professionals from four hospitals participated in the study: Leady Reading Hospital (54.7%), Hayatabad Medical Complex (29.3%), Institute of Kidney Disease (8.7%), and Maqsood Medical Complex Hospital (7.3%). The majority were Anesthesia Technologists (48%), followed by Trainee Doctors/Medical Officers (34%), Senior Consultants/Professors (9.3%), Junior Consultants (4.7%), and Heads of Departments (4%).

Most participants had less than 3 years (35.3%) or 3-5 years (21.3%) of professional experience, while a smaller proportion had 6-10 years (18%), 11-15 years (11.3%), or over 15 years (14%). Leady Reading Hospital employed the highest number of professionals across all designations and experience levels. Notably, Anesthesia Technologists were predominantly based in Hayatabad Medical Complex, while most senior roles and longer experience durations were concentrated in Leady Reading Hospital and Institute of Kidney Disease.

Figure 1 (demographics of participants)

Figure 2 (participants experience)

Considering Environmental impact of anesthesia

The data on how often anesthesia professionals consider the environmental impact when choosing an anesthetic technique provides key insights into clinical decision-making behavior. Among the 150 respondents, 61 individuals (40.7%) reported that they always consider environmental factors during anesthetic selection. This

was followed by 35 respondents (23.3%) who frequently take such considerations into account, and 18 participants (12.0%) who do so occasionally. However, 26 respondents (17.3%) admitted to rarely considering environmental impact, while 10 individuals (6.7%) reported never considering it at all.

Figure 3 (considering environmental impact)

Awareness about the environmental impact of anesthesia

The data concerning respondents' awareness of the environmental impact of anesthesia reveals that a majority of participants (n = 97; 64.7%) reported being

aware of the ecological consequences associated with anesthetic practices. In contrast, 53 respondents (35.3%) indicated that they were not aware of the environmental impact of anesthesia.

Figure 4 (awareness)

But in order to verify the claims of those who said they were aware of the environmental impact of anesthesia a question was included in the questionnaire to check their knowledge whether their answers were true or they were just making false claims so we asked them about the least environmental anesthetic technique which is obviously peripheral nerve blocks followed by total

intravenous anesthesia (alternative to inhalational anesthesia) so the results were that the 97 anesthesia professionals who reported being aware of the environmental impact of anesthesia, 11 individuals (11.3%) provided incorrect answers by selecting either low-flow volatile anesthesia or high-flow volatile anesthesia as the least environmentally harmful

techniques. This discrepancy suggests that some respondents may overestimate their level of awareness or may have misconceptions regarding the actual environmental impact of different anesthetic practices. This emphasizes the need for focused educational efforts to clarify which techniques are truly sustainable, particularly differentiating between low-emission and high-emission practices.

After validating responses against correct knowledge, the effective or *true* awareness of the environmental impact of anesthesia among the study participants is approximately 57.3%, which is notably lower than the initial self-reported awareness of 64.7%. This highlights a knowledge gap where some anesthesia professionals may believe they are informed but lack accurate understanding, underscoring the need for targeted educational interventions to improve actual awareness.

Figure 5 (cross checking)

Formal training in sustainable Anesthesia practices

The analysis of respondents' exposure to formal training in sustainable anesthesia practices reveals a nearly even distribution. Out of the total 150 participants, 76 individuals (50.7%) reported having received formal training related to environmentally sustainable anesthetic practices, while 74 participants (49.3%) indicated that they had not received any such training. These finding suggests a marginal training gap in the professional development of anesthesia personnel regarding environmental sustainability. Although it is encouraging that half of the respondents have been formally trained, the other half remains without

structured education on this critical topic. The absence of training in nearly 49.3% of respondents may contribute to inconsistent implementation of sustainable practices, despite the growing environmental concerns associated with anesthetic gases and materials.

These results emphasize the need for standardized inclusion of sustainability modules in both academic curricula and institutional continuing education programs. Ensuring that all anesthesia professionals are equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary to make environmentally responsible clinical decisions is essential for fostering a sustainable healthcare system.

Figure 6 (formal training)

Addressing environmental sustainability

The data assessing beliefs about professional responsibility toward environmental sustainability in anesthesia shows a generally positive attitude among respondents. Out of the 150 anesthesia professionals surveyed, 65 individuals (43.3%) stated that they strongly agree anesthesia professionals have a responsibility to address environmental sustainability, while 52 respondents (34.7%) expressed agreement with the statement. Combined, this indicates that 78% of respondents hold a favorable view regarding their professional duty toward environmental stewardship. Meanwhile, 25 participants (16.7%) remained neutral, possibly reflecting uncertainty or lack of clarity about the role of anesthesia in environmental issues. A small minority expressed dissenting opinions: 3 respondents

(2.0%) disagreed, and 5 respondents (3.3%) strongly disagreed, suggesting that these individuals either question the relevance of sustainability in anesthesia or do not view it as a professional obligation.

This distribution highlights a strong overall consensus (nearly four out of five professionals) that anesthesia providers do indeed share responsibility in mitigating healthcare's environmental impact. However, the presence of neutral and disagreeing opinions suggests an opportunity to further reinforce this professional ethic through awareness initiatives, integration of environmental content in training curricula, and policy-level reinforcement within institutions. Strengthening this sense of responsibility is key to promoting consistent adoption of sustainable practices in anesthetic care.

Figure 7 (addressing environmental sustainability)

Institutional policies

The data concerning institutional support for environmentally sustainable anesthetic practices reveals a lack of clarity and consistency across healthcare

settings. Out of 150 anesthesia professionals surveyed, only 55 respondents (36.7%) confirmed that their institutions provide formal guidelines or policies promoting sustainable anesthetic practices. Meanwhile,

51 participants (34.0%) reported that their institutions do not have such policies in place. Notably, 44

individuals (29.3%) stated they are not sure whether such institutional policies existed.

Figure 8 (institutional policies)

Inclusion on sustainable practices

The data regarding support for the inclusion of sustainability metrics in anesthesia practice assessments demonstrates a largely favorable attitude among anesthesia professionals. Out of the total 150 respondents, 65 individuals (43.3%) strongly agreed, and 49 respondents (32.7%) agreed that sustainability metrics should be integrated into the evaluation of anesthesia practices. Combined, 76% of participants expressed positive support for this initiative.

In contrast, 29 respondents (19.3%) selected a neutral position, possibly reflecting uncertainty or a lack of familiarity with what such metrics would entail. Only a small minority were opposed: 6 respondents (4.0%)

disagreed, and 1 respondent (0.7%) strongly disagreed, indicating minimal resistance to the concept.

These findings suggest that a substantial majority of anesthesia professionals are receptive to formalizing environmental sustainability as a component of clinical quality and performance assessment. The support for integrating sustainable metrics underscores a growing recognition of the importance of environmentally responsible healthcare and suggests readiness for institutional and policy-level changes. Incorporating sustainability indicators into anesthesia audits, accreditation criteria, and professional evaluations could help drive systemic improvements, reinforce accountability, and align clinical practice with broader environmental goals.

Figure 9 (sustainable practices assessment)

Training and awareness in sustainable anesthesia

The data assessing the willingness of anesthesia professionals to receive further training and awareness on sustainable developed practices in the operation theatre (OT) reveals a strong positive inclination. Out of the 150 participants surveyed, an overwhelming 132

individuals (88.0%) expressed a desire to be more trained and informed about environmentally sustainable practices applicable within the OR setting. In contrast, only 18 respondents (12.0%) indicated that they would not be interested in further training on this subject.

Figure 10 (training and awareness)

The findings of this study indicate that while a majority of anesthesia professionals demonstrate a general awareness of the environmental impact of anesthesia (64.7%), only 57.3% accurately identified environmentally sustainable practices such as peripheral nerve blocks and total intravenous anesthesia, suggesting a gap between perceived and actual knowledge. Approximately half (50.7%) of the respondents reported receiving formal training in sustainable anesthesia, and 76% consider environmental impact in their anesthetic decisions to varying degrees. Furthermore, 78% believe that anesthesia professionals hold a responsibility to address environmental sustainability, though only 36.7% confirmed the presence of institutional policies supporting such practices, with 29.3% uncertain. A significant majority (76%) supported the inclusion of sustainability metrics in practice assessments, and 88% expressed willingness to receive further training on sustainable developed practices in the operation theatre. These results highlight both a promising level of engagement and a critical need for enhanced education, institutional support, and policy integration to promote environmentally responsible anesthesia practices. The true or validated awareness of anesthesia professionals regarding the environmental impact of anesthesia, based on correct knowledge, is 57.3%, whereas the self-reported awareness stands at 64.7%. This discrepancy highlights a knowledge gap that must be addressed through targeted education and training.

Discussion

The findings of this cross-sectional study provide significant insights into the current state of awareness and practices related to environmental sustainability among anesthesia professionals in tertiary care hospitals across Peshawar. The data reveal both encouraging trends and critical gaps that merit attention for educational and policy-level reforms. One of the central findings of the study is that while a majority (64.7%) of anesthesia professionals reported being aware of the environmental impact of anesthetic practices, only 57.3% demonstrated validated knowledge when asked to identify the least environmentally harmful techniques. This discrepancy between self-perceived and actual knowledge reflects a broader pattern observed in international studies. For instance, Baumann et al. (2022) reported that although 94.2% of anesthesiologists in a German hospital acknowledged the threat of climate change, a significant portion were unfamiliar with the environmental effects of commonly used anesthetic agents and low-flow techniques(21). This knowledge gap underscores the importance of targeted educational interventions to convert general awareness into evidence-based clinical decision-making. The results also indicate that approximately half of the participants (50.7%) had received formal training on sustainable anesthesia practices. However, a substantial 49.3% had not received any structured education on this subject, which likely contributes to the inconsistencies in

knowledge and practice. These findings are consistent with Santos et al. (2024), who identified inadequate education (62.6%) as one of the primary barriers to the implementation of green practices in Portuguese operating rooms (1). Encouragingly, 88% of participants in this study expressed a willingness to undergo further training, reflecting a high level of professional motivation to adopt environmentally sustainable behaviors. This presents a timely opportunity for curriculum developers and hospital administrators to introduce training modules focusing on sustainability principles, low-emission techniques, and waste reduction strategies.

Institutional support for environmentally sustainable practices emerged as another area of concern. Only 36.7% of participants affirmed that their institutions provided formal guidelines or policies promoting sustainable anesthesia. In contrast, 29.3% were uncertain about the existence of such policies, and 34.0% reported their absence altogether. This finding aligns with global trends highlighted by Sherman et al. (2022), who emphasized the lack of institutional and infrastructural support as a critical barrier to environmental sustainability in anesthesia (17). Without clear policies and protocols, individual efforts toward green practices remain fragmented and inconsistent. Therefore, institutional engagement, including the development of formal sustainability protocols, regular audits, and the integration of environmental metrics in performance evaluations, is essential to foster systemic change.

An important aspect revealed by this study is the perception of responsibility among anesthesia professionals regarding environmental sustainability. A substantial majority (78%) either agreed or strongly agreed that they bear a professional responsibility to address environmental concerns. This finding supports prior observations by Gasciauskaite et al. (2023), who noted that anesthesia providers generally value sustainability but often face systemic challenges in implementing their intentions(3). Furthermore, 76% of respondents supported the inclusion of sustainability metrics in professional assessments, reinforcing the notion that environmental stewardship should be embedded within clinical governance and quality improvement frameworks.

The study also highlighted misconceptions regarding the environmental impact of anesthetic agents and techniques. Although the most sustainable techniques include peripheral nerve blocks and total intravenous anesthesia (TIVA), 11.3% of participants incorrectly identified low-flow or high-flow volatile anesthesia as

environmentally preferable. This misperception can have real-world implications, as volatile agents such as desflurane and nitrous oxide have disproportionately high global warming potentials (GWPs). For example, desflurane's GWP over a 100-year horizon is 2,540 times that of carbon dioxide (8). Wyssusek et al. (2022) demonstrated that interventions such as desflurane elimination and staff education could lead to an 87.88% reduction in anesthesia-related greenhouse gas emissions (22). Therefore, accurate knowledge dissemination is essential to reduce the carbon footprint of operating rooms.

Moreover, this study found that 40.7% of anesthesia professionals always consider environmental impact in their anesthetic choices, while 23.3% do so frequently. This suggests a growing recognition of the need to balance clinical efficacy with environmental responsibility. These findings are comparable to the behavioral trends reported by Zaw et al. (2023), where despite awareness, the implementation of green practices was hindered by contextual barriers such as lack of time, resources, and senior support(23). Consequently, it is vital to create a workplace culture that prioritizes environmental considerations alongside patient safety and clinical outcomes.

The high level of interest in sustainability training (88% willing to receive further education) indicates readiness for institutional and academic engagement. Educational bodies, including universities and training hospitals, should take proactive steps to incorporate sustainability into undergraduate and postgraduate curricula. Furthermore, hospitals should facilitate regular workshops, simulation training, and inclusion of sustainability modules in continuing medical education (CME) programs to reinforce knowledge and application.

Lastly, this study aligns with global environmental goals, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 (Climate Action) and WHO's agenda for climate-resilient health systems. By promoting sustainable anesthetic practices, healthcare institutions can significantly reduce their ecological footprint, improve occupational safety by reducing exposure to waste anesthetic gases, and potentially decrease operational costs through efficient resource utilization (12,18,24).

Conclusion

This study assessed environmental sustainability awareness among anesthesia professionals in tertiary care hospitals across Peshawar, revealing a critical link between clinical practice and environmental

responsibility. While 64.7% of respondents acknowledged the environmental impact of anesthetic practices, only 57.3% correctly identified the most sustainable technique peripheral nerve blocks and total intravenous anesthesia highlighting a gap between perceived awareness and actual knowledge, a trend seen globally (21,25). About 50.7% had formal training in sustainable anesthesia, yet 88% expressed willingness to pursue further education, presenting an opportunity for institutions to introduce structured sustainability modules. Although 76% supported integrating sustainability metrics into clinical assessments, only 36.7% reported existing institutional policies, underscoring the need for system-wide implementation backed by leadership and regulatory frameworks (1,17,22). Encouragingly, 78% viewed environmental responsibility as a professional duty, reflecting a global shift toward accountability (3,17). These findings affirm a readiness among Peshawar's anesthesia professionals to adopt sustainable practices, contingent on improved education, defined policies, and institutional support, aligning Pakistan's healthcare efforts with the UN Sustainable Development Goals particularly SDG 13 (Climate Action) and SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being) (8,24).

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